

Research On The Go

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Software

- [SORSE](#)
- [Event Website](#)

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Software for research comes in many different forms and technologies. This includes software that runs on mobile devices. The demand for this is growing, whether it is for “citizen-science” projects or in clinical and educational research. In this SORSE (online) roundtable event, we discuss * examples of mobile apps for research * what are the challenges for mobile apps in and for research. In particular: * logistic of deploying and delivering mobile apps * maintenance costs * distribution of apps - what are the options * how to build the right team for mobile apps development * what technology stacks are used in mobile app development. And what determines the choice? Note: this event will be recorded for a podcast.

Panelists

- Adrian Harwood, University of Manchester, established and manages the Mobile Development Service (MDS) in the RSE group.
- Peter Schmidt, University College London, has been an app developer in the private sector and now at UCL.
- Mark Turner, University of Newcastle, leads mobile development efforts in his RSE group.
- Patricia Barnby, University of Manchester, full time mobile app developer and member of the MDS since its conception.